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Estimation of $\Delta\chi^2$ from the Fourier parameters and information matrix

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INTRODUCTION

For a single star, the Fourier parameters of the light modulation behind the main grid are expected to satisfy two conditions, supposedly known from the OTF-calibration. Roughly speaking, these conditions are

- (i) that the first and second harmonics are in phase with each other;
- (ii) that the ratio of their amplitudes is a constant and known number.

(We disregard here that there might be a small and known phase difference, and the variations of this difference and the amplitude ratio with colour and position in the field.)

For a double or multiple star, no such simple relations between the Fourier parameters can be postulated [since the phase difference and amplitude ratio are functions of the (unknown) object parameters, such as separation and magnitude difference.] For these objects, a five-parameter signal model is thus appropriate,

$$N_{\ell} \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos H_{\ell} + b_3 \sin H_{\ell} + b_4 \cos 2H_{\ell} + b_5 \sin 2H_{\ell} \quad (\underline{b}) \quad (1)$$

where $\{N_{\ell}\}$ are the photon counts and $\{H_{\ell}\}$ the relative phases for each sample (or bin), and $\underline{b} = (b_1 \ b_2 \ b_3 \ b_4 \ b_5)^T$ is the five-dimensional parameter vector.

Imposing the constraints (i)-(ii) onto the ML-fit of the model (1) to a given set of data will always result in a poorer fit than the free model (1). This can be measured by the increased χ^2 , that is $\Delta\chi^2 = (\chi^2)_{\text{constr}} - (\chi^2)_{\text{free}}$. This note is concerned with estimating this $\Delta\chi^2$ directly from a ML-fit of (1) to (binned or unbinned) photon counts, and with the statistical representation of this quantity. This is primarily of interest for the double-star simulations, but the proposed summary statistics may be convenient also in the real processing.

THE LIKELIHOOD FUNCTION

Assuming that the photon counts follow the Poisson distribution with intensity I_ℓ , the likelihood function of any parameter vector $\underline{b}$ is

$$\lambda(\underline{b}) = \prod_{\ell} (N_{\ell}!)^{-1} (I_{\ell})^{N_{\ell}} \exp(-I_{\ell}) \quad (2)$$

We prefer working with the log-likelihood function

$$L(\underline{b}) = \sum_{\ell} \left[N_{\ell} \ln I_{\ell} - I_{\ell} \right] \quad (3)$$

in which we have left out the constant term, $-\sum_{\ell} \ln(N_{\ell}!)$.

THE LIKELIHOOD RATIO TEST

We are interested in testing the hypothesis H_0 : that the star is single, against the more general hypothesis H_A : that of an arbitrary object ($H_0 \subset H_A$). In terms of the parameter space for $\underline{b}$, the general hypothesis H_A corresponds to the whole volume in which $\underline{b}$ would yield non-negative intensities [e.g., $b_1 \geq f(b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5)$], while H_0 corresponds to the subset of that volume which in addition satisfies the conditions (i) - (ii).

For the likelihood ratio test we obtain the ML estimates of $\underline{b}$ under the two hypotheses, $\hat{\underline{b}}_0$ and $\hat{\underline{b}}_A$:

$$\lambda(\hat{\underline{b}}_0) = \sup_{\underline{b} \in H_0} \lambda(\underline{b}), \quad \lambda(\hat{\underline{b}}_A) = \sup_{\underline{b} \in H_A} \lambda(\underline{b}) \quad (4)$$

and compute the likelihood ratio $\Lambda = \lambda(\hat{\underline{b}}_0) / \lambda(\hat{\underline{b}}_A)$. The asymptotic distribution of $-2 \ln \Lambda$, given that H_0 is true, is known to be that of the chi-square variable with $p = \dim(H_A) - \dim(H_0)$ degrees of freedom. This can be used to compute a critical value for Λ , above which H_0 should be rejected.

In our case, $p = 2$ corresponding to the conditions (i) - (ii). Thus we can expect the statistic

$$\Delta\chi^2 = -2 [L(\hat{\underline{b}}_0) - L(\hat{\underline{b}}_A)] \quad (5)$$

to follow the χ^2 -distribution with 2 d.o.f., if the star is single; otherwise, $\Delta\chi^2$ will tend to get larger.

APPROXIMATIONS

In the double star simulations, as well as in the real processing of the photon counts, the intensity model (1) is fitted by ML without any constraint on the parameter vector $\underline{b}$. The resulting estimate corresponds to hypothesis H_A above and is denoted $\hat{\underline{b}}_A$ or simply $\hat{\underline{b}}$ for brevity. However, we do not explicitly fit a single-star model (hypothesis H_0) to the photon counts, but use (in the Location Estimator of the real processing) an approximate expansion to derive the constrained estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}_0$ and $\Delta\chi^2$. The approach used in the Location Estimator is not suitable for the present double-star experiments, however, mainly because it is formulated in terms of the modified signal parameters β_1 to β_5 rather than b_1 to b_5 . Accordingly, I derive below approximations for $\hat{\underline{b}}_0$ and $\Delta\chi^2$ directly from the ML model used to compute $\hat{\underline{b}}$.

In the vicinity of the unconstrained estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}$ we adopt a second-order Taylor expansion of the log-likelihood function $L(\underline{b})$:

$$L(\underline{b}) = L(\hat{\underline{b}}) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta \underline{b}' \left(\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \underline{b} \partial \underline{b}'} \right)_{\underline{b}=\hat{\underline{b}}} \Delta \underline{b} \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta \underline{b} = \underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}}$. (Note that $\partial L / \partial \underline{b} = \underline{0}$ by virtue of the ML condition, hence the absence of the first-order term in the expansion.) From (3) we find

$$\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \underline{b} \partial \underline{b}'} = \sum_{\ell} \left[\left(\frac{N_{\ell}}{I_{\ell}} - 1 \right) \frac{\partial^2 I_{\ell}}{\partial \underline{b} \partial \underline{b}'} - \frac{N_{\ell}}{I_{\ell}^2} \frac{\partial I_{\ell}}{\partial \underline{b}} \frac{\partial I_{\ell}}{\partial \underline{b}'} \right] \quad (7)$$

Usually this expression is replaced by its expectation, which is obtained by setting $E(N_{\ell}) = I_{\ell}$. The negative of the resulting matrix is known as the information matrix:

$$\underline{F} = - E \left(\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \underline{b} \partial \underline{b}'} \right) = \sum_{\ell} \frac{1}{I_{\ell}} \frac{\partial I_{\ell}}{\partial \underline{b}} \frac{\partial I_{\ell}}{\partial \underline{b}'} \quad (8)$$

and it is evaluated for $\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}}$ as part of the likelihood iteration. (Its inverse is the estimated variance-covariance matrix of $\hat{\underline{b}}$.) Replacing (7) by its expectation is only a slight inaccuracy, and may even be an advantage in that the fluctuations of N_{ℓ} will not enter the computations directly (only via the corresponding uncertainty of $\hat{\underline{b}}$).

Combining (8), (6) and (5) we find that the increase in chi-square when going from $\hat{\underline{b}}$ to some nearby parameter vector $\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}} + \underline{\Delta b}$ is approximately

$$\Delta\chi^2 = \underline{\Delta b}' \underline{F} \underline{\Delta b} \quad (9)$$

We must now find the permissible range of $\underline{\Delta b}$ under H_0 , i.e. under conditions (i) - (ii), and minimize (9) subject to this constraint. The resulting vector $\hat{\underline{b}} + \underline{\Delta b}$ will be our approximation of $\hat{\underline{b}}_0$, and the corresponding $\Delta\chi^2$ is our estimate of (5).

Given the ratio $R = M_2/M_1$ of the amplitudes of the harmonics, and the phase difference v_2 , the constrained (single-star) model can be written

$$I_\ell = b_1 + (b_2^2 + b_3^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\cos(H_\ell - \phi) + R \cos(2H_\ell - 2\phi - v_2) \right] \quad (10)$$

where $\phi = \text{ATAN2}(b_3, b_2)$. Comparison with (1) shows that this model applies if b_4 and b_5 satisfy

$$b_4 = (b_2^2 + b_3^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} R [(b_2^2 - b_3^2) \cos v_2 - 2b_2 b_3 \sin v_2] \quad (11a)$$

$$b_5 = (b_2^2 + b_3^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} R [(b_2^2 - b_3^2) \sin v_2 + 2b_2 b_3 \cos v_2] \quad (11b)$$

In the following I assume $v_2 = 0$ for simplicity, although the generalization to non-zero phase difference is trivial.

Considering that the first harmonic is generally much better determined than the second, a reasonable first approximation to $\hat{\underline{b}}_0$ is obtained simply by retaining b_1 , b_2 and b_3 from $\hat{\underline{b}}$, and setting b_4 and b_5 to the values implied by (11). This gives for the difference vector

$$\underline{\Delta b}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ R(\hat{b}_2^2 - \hat{b}_3^2)(\hat{b}_2^2 + \hat{b}_3^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \hat{b}_4 \\ 2R\hat{b}_2\hat{b}_3(\hat{b}_2^2 + \hat{b}_3^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \hat{b}_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The subscript $_0$ here indicates a first approximation. For we can certainly reduce $\Delta\chi^2$ a bit further by allowing also the first three components to

become non-zero, say $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_3$. In doing so, we must however change also the last two components of $\underline{\Delta b}$ in such a way that (11a) and (11b) are still satisfied. Using a linear expansion of (11) around the point $(\hat{b}_2, \hat{b}_3)$ we find that the required changes in b_4 and b_5 are:

$$\Delta b_4 = \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_2} \epsilon_2 + \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_3} \epsilon_3, \quad \Delta b_5 = \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_2} \epsilon_2 + \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_3} \epsilon_3 \quad (13)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_2} &= R\hat{b}_2(\hat{b}_2^2 + 3\hat{b}_3^2)S^{-3}, & \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_3} &= -R\hat{b}_3(3\hat{b}_2^2 + \hat{b}_3^2)S^{-3}, \\ \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_2} &= 2R\hat{b}_3^3 S^{-3}, & \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_3} &= 2R\hat{b}_2^3 S^{-3} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

and $S = (\hat{b}_2^2 + \hat{b}_3^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. A difference vector $\underline{\Delta b}$ approximately satisfying (11) for arbitrary $\underline{\epsilon} = (\epsilon_1 \ \epsilon_2 \ \epsilon_3)'$ can therefore be written in matrix form as

$$\underline{\Delta b} = \underline{\Delta b}_0 + \underline{C} \underline{\epsilon} \quad (15)$$

where $\underline{C}$ is the 5×3 matrix

$$\underline{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_2} & \frac{\partial u_4}{\partial b_3} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_2} & \frac{\partial u_5}{\partial b_3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Inserting (15) in (9) we have

$$\Delta \chi^2 = \underline{\Delta b}_0' \underline{F} \underline{\Delta b}_0 + 2 \underline{\epsilon}' \underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{\Delta b}_0 + \underline{\epsilon}' \underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{C} \underline{\epsilon} \quad (17)$$

Since $\underline{\epsilon}$ is unconstrained under H_0 (provided it is not too large), the minimizing vector is easily found to be

$$\underline{\epsilon} = -(\underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{C})^{-1} \underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{\Delta b}_0 \quad (18)$$

corresponding to the value

$$\Delta\chi^2 = \Delta\underline{b}_0' \underline{F} \Delta\underline{b}_0 - \Delta\underline{b}_0' \underline{F} \underline{C} (\underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{C})^{-1} \underline{C}' \underline{F} \Delta\underline{b}_0 \quad (19)$$

For the practical evaluation of (18) and (19), the following method can be used. Define the 5×4 matrix

$$\underline{D} = (\underline{C} \quad \Delta\underline{b}_0) \quad (20)$$

and compute the upper-diagonal part of the symmetric 4×4 matrix

$$\underline{D}' \underline{F} \underline{D} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{C}' \underline{F} \underline{C} & \underline{C}' \underline{F} \Delta\underline{b}_0 \\ .. & \Delta\underline{b}_0' \underline{F} \Delta\underline{b}_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Performing a Cholesky reduction (triangularization) of this matrix results in an upper-triangular matrix with $(\Delta\chi^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in the bottom-right corner. Solving the triangular system formed by the first three rows of the reduced matrix gives the vector $-\underline{\epsilon}$.

HISTOGRAM PRESENTATION OF $\Delta\chi^2$

In the real processing, an independent value of $\Delta\chi^2$ is computed for every frame in which a given star is observed. For the entire mission, there are thus several hundred (up to a few thousand) $\Delta\chi^2$ -values for each star. The combination of these statistics is expected to give a powerful indication of duplicity. It is not obvious however how the many $\Delta\chi^2$ -values for a given star should be combined in a manner which is both statistically efficient and practically manageable.

From a purely statistical point of view, assuming perfect data, the optimal combination is simply the sum of all $\Delta\chi^2$. This should be a chi-square variable (under H_0) with $2n$ degrees of freedom, if n is the number of observations (frames) collected. With a certain fraction of corrupt data, this method will not be acceptable: a small number of 'bad' frames, yielding perhaps abnormally large $\Delta\chi^2$ -values, could easily set off a false alarm on a perfectly single star. It is wise, therefore to retain some more information on the actual distribution of $\Delta\chi^2$ -values than just the mean value.

The proposed solution is a simple histogram representation of $\Delta\chi^2$, using eight bins. These are chosen such that equal numbers are expected if the star is really single (i.e., if $\Delta\chi^2$ is a chi-square variable with 2 d.o.f.). If we number the bins 0, 1, ..., 7, we may compute the bin number according to the formula

$$\text{ibin} = \text{MIN}(7, \text{INT}(8 \cdot \text{EXP}(-0.5 \cdot \Delta\chi^2))) \quad (22)$$

A predominance of large $\Delta\chi^2$ -values, as we might have for many double and multiple stars, would result in an excess of small bin numbers.

Clearly this representation is very robust. It retains the most important information about the actual distribution while requiring only a modest (and fixed) number of integers to be accumulated for each star. Moreover, it is comparatively easy to devise various statistical tests on histogram data, as compared with moments (for instance). A possible drawback is that there is no differentiation among the large $\Delta\chi^2$ -values, namely in bin 0 ($\Delta\chi^2 > 4.159$), while there is perhaps too much differentiation for the small values. (In other words, should we aim at histogram equalization not for single stars, but for some 'moderately double' star?)

NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

A number of numerical experiments was made in order to test the validity of $\Delta\chi^2$ as computed from (19) and the usefulness of the histogram representation. The experiments were carried out with a separate *ad hoc* program written in BASIC and run on a personal computer. It simulates 100 frames of photon counts obtained by scanning a given object in random directions (having a uniform distribution from 0 to 2π). Each frame corresponds to a different scan direction and was preprocessed to give the unconstrained vector $\hat{b}$ and associated information matrix $\underline{F}$. Then $\Delta\chi^2$ was calculated from (14), (16), and (19) and a histogram of ibin [from (22)] accumulated. Parameters of the 24 different objects are listed in Table 1 and the histograms are displayed in Figures 1.1 to 3.8.

The distribution of $\Delta\chi^2$ is clearly skewed for all objects with separations greater than some 0.2 to 0.3 arcsec (depending on the magnitudes). A simple indication of skewness could be the statistic

$$t = (2m - n - 1)/n^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (23)$$

which should be approximately $N(0,1)$ if the star is single. Here, n is the total number of frames ($n = 100$) and m is the number of frames with $\text{ibin} \leq 3$ [The exact distribution of m under H_0 is binomial with parameters n and $p = 0.5$; hence the mean is np and variance $np(1-p)$.] The statistic t is also given in each histogram plot below the object parameters and in Table 1. $t > 3$ might be considered a significant deviation from the single-star hypothesis.

Table 1. Object parameters and skewness t for the histograms 1.1 to 3.8.

Figure	primary B-mag	mag. diff Δm	separation ρ ["]	skewness t
1.1	9.0	1.0	0.0	0.5
1.2	"	"	0.1	1.7
1.3	"	"	0.2	4.7
1.4	"	"	0.3	5.5
1.5	"	"	0.6	7.7
1.6	"	"	1.2	7.9
1.7	"	"	1.8	6.7
1.8	"	"	15.0	7.1
2.1	9.0	2.0	0.0	-0.1
2.2	"	"	0.1	0.7
2.3	"	"	0.2	0.1
2.4	"	"	0.3	2.5
2.5	"	"	0.6	7.1
2.6	"	"	1.2	5.3
2.7	"	"	1.8	6.5
2.8	"	"	15.0	5.3
3.1	11.0	1.0	0.0	0.3
3.2	"	"	0.1	-0.3
3.3	"	"	0.2	1.3
3.4	"	"	0.3	4.1
3.5	"	"	0.6	7.3
3.6	"	"	1.2	4.5
3.7	"	"	1.8	6.3
3.8	"	"	15.0	5.1

That the particular statistic t is probably not optimal for recognizing non-single stars is illustrated by the case in Figure 2.4, which definitely appears to be skew, although $t = 2.5$ only. Possibly it is better to form the statistic from $\text{ibin} \leq 1$ (say), rather than $\text{ibin} \leq 3$ as in (23). But such considerations need not be made in advance of the real data, if the complete histogram is computed for every star.

Figure 1.1 to 1.8. Histograms for objects with primary B = 9, $\Delta m = 1$, and increasing separation (0 to 15")

2.1

2.2

2.3

2.4

2.5

2.6

2.7

2.8

Figure 2.1 to 2.8. Histograms for objects with primary B = 9, $\Delta m = 2$, and increasing separation (0 to 15").

3.1

3.2

3.3

3.4

3.5

3.6

3.7

3.8

Figure 3.1 to 3.8. Histograms for objects with primary B = 11, $\Delta m = 1$, and increasing separation (0 to 15")